

ACTUALITY AND DIRECTIONS FOR THE FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Despite the wide possibilities of motivation for health-saving behavior of students, at present there are still problems of its formation, due to both social and cultural characteristics. The main factors influencing the formation of the lifestyle of young people are the family, the social environment, the media and communications. The article provides an analysis based on surveys of students around the world. Students, in particular, confirm the significant influence of the environment on both initiation into bad habits and healthy hobbies. The main factors hindering a healthy lifestyle of students include the lack of free time, the material component, Internet addiction, lack of sufficient motivation and self-organization.

A healthy lifestyle is important not only for students, but for all mankind. Great work is being done in our country in this direction. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 30.10.2020 "On measures for the widespread implementation of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports" No. PF-6099.¹ Ensuring that every citizen has a strong immune system against the disease through regular physical activity and mass sports, as well as the formation of life skills for a healthy lifestyle, the abandonment of harmful habits, In order to comply with the principles of nutrition, rehabilitation and rehabilitation, as well as the systematic and effective organization of mass physical

activity, a number of tasks have been identified to create the appropriate infrastructure and other necessary conditions.

The activity and viability of a modern person, the duration and quality of his life largely depend on his health. This relationship is recognized as extremely important everywhere. This can be confirmed not only by the emergence of numerous sports and health institutions, fitness clubs, sports sections, but also by various government projects and programs in which the main and significant attention is paid to the health of the population.²

If we consider the issue of public health in a comprehensive manner, then

¹ www.lex.uz

² Student youth perception of health (the results of a survey)] // Moscow, 2014. p. 317—320.

we should note the mutual influence of health and lifestyle of people. From the point of view of medicine, human health is more than half (50-55%) dependent on lifestyle, 20% on the environment, 18-20% on genetic predisposition, and 8-10% on healthcare organization. . Moreover, a person's lifestyle is not only a key aspect of human health, but also a factor that can be personally controlled or adjusted.

The health of young people as a special socio-demographic group is a strategic potential of any society. This is the key to the reproductive, economic and cultural future of the country. If we talk about student youth (namely, this social group was the object of our study), it is important to note that the training of highly qualified personnel is impossible without taking into account their state of health. Moreover, for student youth, the risks associated with threats to health are very high. It is necessary to take into account not only intense mental and psycho-emotional stress during study at a university, but also adaptive changes associated with physiological and social processes taking place during this period of a person's life.

Let's analyze the results of a survey of students around the world.

It is necessary to find out what students specifically invest in the concept of healthy lifestyle, how they perceive and interpret it. To clarify the content of this category, first of all, we will give the healthy lifestyle components mentioned by the respondents:

- no bad habits (drinking alcohol and smoking),
- Complete abstinence from drug use
- a balanced and regular diet,
- constant physical activity,

- a rational daily routine (work and rest schedule, good sleep),
- regular health monitoring,
- mental balance (constructive resistance to stress).

The presence of bad habits and the use of any drugs, according to all participants in the study, clearly contradicts a healthy lifestyle. To bad habits participants of the study, first of all, attributed smoking. Then there was mention of alcohol abuse, or the use of alcohol in general. Part of the respondents attributed to bad habits, overeating and Internet addiction. According to the absolute majority of respondents, smoking and a healthy lifestyle are incompatible, because this is a very pernicious habit, the negative consequences of which will certainly manifest themselves in the future. But there is another position associated, for example, with smoking a hookah.

Narcotic substances, even in this context, are a very specific and separate topic. Probably, due to the sensitivity of this topic, the participants in the study practically did not discuss it.³

A balanced and regular diet is a key component of a healthy lifestyle. Almost all participants in the study agreed with this: "Some even start their healthy lifestyle with nutrition. They start to exclude some products, for example.

"Proper and healthy" nutrition implies a certain regularity of meals and their balance in volume, and the diet should meet the needs of a particular person in a particular period of time, including depending on the environment and occupation:

³ Aripova S.Kh., "Physiology and hygiene of youth" T.: "Science and technology" 2010.

"If for an athlete who trains very intensively, then carbohydrates. For an athlete involved in power sports, squirrels."

The regularity of meals for a person adhering to a healthy lifestyle varies from 5-6 to 3-4 times a day. The timing of meals is also important.⁴

Meals should be balanced in volume - a nutritious breakfast, a hearty and full lunch (including the first course), and dinner, on the contrary, is modest.

The diet of a person adhering to a healthy lifestyle should be balanced, include mainly vegetables, fruits, cereals, cereals, nuts, and fish. It is necessary to limit the consumption of sweet, fatty, flour, fast food, etc. The method of cooking is also important - fried, smoked, pickled foods and dishes should not dominate the diet. The quality of food, according to respondents, is also important. Drinking regime was mentioned as a separate item in two focus groups. To maintain optimal balance in the body, it is necessary to drink enough fluid daily, but it is important to minimize the consumption of sugary and carbonated drinks.

In addition, the use of energy drinks is extremely negatively assessed by the respondents. Such drinks contain substances that forcibly release the reserve reserves of the body, which is extremely harmful. The negative effects of energy drinks that are not obvious at a young age are likely to manifest themselves later.

In the context of nutrition, one of the discussions touched upon the topic of vegetarianism, including due to the participation of a respondent who refused

to eat meat products. Vegetarianism itself and its varieties (veganism, raw food diet, lacto-vegetarianism), as well as other special nutritional practices, are perceived differently and ambiguously by people, including due to insufficient awareness of this issue. However, in the youth environment, such behavior is perceived mostly calmly, but not without irony.

Regular physical activity is an important component of a healthy lifestyle for a significant part of the respondents. The participants of the study paid special attention to the optimality of physical activity in the context of the general state of the body of a particular person. Moreover, professional or too intense sports, from the point of view of some respondents, do not correspond to the concept of a healthy lifestyle, because they often lead to the opposite result - overstrain of the body and, possibly, serious injuries. Which can lead to negative consequences in the future. As an example, the respondents mentioned the sport of high achievements and cited the experience of familiar professional athletes as an example: "Sport for what? There is sport in the name of health, and there is sport in the name of some benefit. If we take athletes, then the main thing for them is victory. They tear their ligaments, etc. This cannot be called a healthy lifestyle for your health. They do it for something else. To get some kind of title, to earn money, perhaps. There is a division into a healthy life, a healthy lifestyle, and just sports.

The optimality of physical activity and other physical activity is defined by respondents in different ways: from daily training and mandatory morning exercises to elementary walks in the fresh air or walking up stairs (instead of using

⁴ M. Akhmatov, "Effective management of public sports in the system of continuing education" "Science and Technology" Tashkent 2015.

elevators) or escalators: "The minimum things we can do. For example, walking up the stairs."

A kind of compromise is the opinion about training sessions lasting 1.5-2 hours with a regularity of 3-4 times a week. The possibility of both individual and group lessons in sports sections or independently is being considered. All these opinions are fundamentally united by the mandatory regularity of classes, and priority is given to anaerobic exercise.⁵

It is in the context of physical activity that Internet addiction (more precisely, dependence on social networks) was often mentioned, which is expressed in a significant lack of physical activity, which leads to health problems, primarily visual impairment and muscle loss. - nogo tone. "Internet is good. Except for the social networks in which you constantly disappear."

The daily routine is one of the key components of a healthy lifestyle, according to the majority of study participants. This implies an optimal mode of work and rest, which must necessarily include a good sleep. Getting enough sleep is the key to good health. Respondents agreed that different people (depending, for example, on age, stress, temperament) need different amounts of time to sleep. The optimal duration of a night's sleep, according to the participants in the study, should be from 6-7 to 10-12 hours.

The daily routine of students is determined, first of all, by the study schedule, which does not always correlate with the rhythm that promotes a healthy lifestyle. The schedule of classes may not

coincide with the usual daily routine, as a result, for example, the time for eating or exercising may change frequently.

Regular health monitoring (passing preventive medical examinations) is a desirable, but not a mandatory component of a healthy lifestyle, according to student representatives. Most of the respondents either did not mention this component at all, or are of the opinion that until something gets sick, they will not deal with health.

Stress management is another component of a healthy lifestyle that was rarely mentioned during the focus groups. Stressful situations accompany modern man everywhere, however, the participants in the study did not pay too much attention to this. Only a part of the respondents consider this aspect worthy of attention and emphasize the importance of the ability to maintain and restore a normal psycho-emotional state in case of nervous overload.

Another typical situation when a person begins to adhere to a healthy lifestyle is the discovery of health problems. In this case, healthy lifestyle is no longer a habit or a need, but becomes a necessity. Medical indications and doctor's recommendations force a person to give up bad habits (if any), follow a diet and daily routine, undergo regular medical examinations, exercise, etc.

Unfortunately, most representatives of student youth do not adhere to a healthy lifestyle. Some young people do not see the need for this and, therefore, do not aspire to such a life expectancy. Some refer to barriers that are difficult to overcome or completely insurmountable, among which one can designate both objective and subjective ones.

⁵ M. Akhmatov, "Effective management of public sports in the system of continuing education" "Science and Technology" Tashkent 2015.

Objective obstacles on the way to a healthy lifestyle, according to the respondents, most often are the nature of the main employment of students, which is predominantly non-physical in nature and, accordingly, is associated with a lack of motor activity, as in most people employed in the field of mental labor. The widespread dependence on social networks and / or the Internet, as well as the need to work at a computer, of course, exacerbate the situation. For some, a serious obstacle to adherence to a diet is the class schedule.

The lack of financial resources, which is typical for students, also acts as an objective barrier to maintaining a healthy lifestyle. "Material security provides more opportunities. If there is enough money, then you can buy gym memberships, eat healthy food - expensive, good, eco-products. And there may even be more time from this."

In addition to this, according to respondents, an objective factor is the lack of time for activities that promote a healthy lifestyle. "I used to lead more healthy lifestyles, but after admission, I no longer."

Lack of time, according to respondents, arises for several reasons, which, in turn, are also divided into objective and subjective. The objective factors include the high intensity of the study load (both classroom and independent work) and significant time spent on moving around the city.⁶

Subjective barriers to a healthy lifestyle include the absence or lack of self-discipline/self-organization and banal laziness. It should be noted that in all focus groups, if not immediately, then by the end

of the discussion, all respondents recognized their own laziness as the primary factor, agreeing with the thesis that: "Forcing yourself is not easy. This requires will. Most people don't have a will now."

Nevertheless, young people during the discussions expressed some suggestions that, in their opinion, can help maintain a healthy lifestyle. In particular, an appropriate environment can serve as a certain insurance against addiction to bad habits.

Thus, it can be stated that a number of factors, both objective and subjective, act as obstacles to maintaining a healthy lifestyle. Overcoming these barriers is possible, first of all, due to the increase in the self-organization of young people and the real awareness of the need for a healthy lifestyle.

In the opinion of the study participants, the incentives for a healthy lifestyle, in addition to habit, necessity, environment or self-awareness, can be fashion and / or promotion of a healthy lifestyle. A separate part of the focus group discussion was devoted to this topic, which showed that modern young people really pay attention to this factor and the promotion of a healthy lifestyle has a certain effect on the youth audience. "Now everything is clear: posters, groups for a healthy lifestyle are being created on the Internet."

Today it is fashionable to monitor your appearance and health, go in for sports or just keep yourself in good physical shape. The active life position of the younger generation makes a significant part of its representatives follow such fashion trends, which undoubtedly contributes to the improvement of youth

⁶ Mamatqulov B. "Public health and health management" "Ilm Ziyoy" publishing house, 2019. Chapter 7 82- 100. Chapter 8 101- 116.

and is expressed in the desire of young people to lead a healthy lifestyle.

On the other hand, the fashion for a healthy lifestyle can also have some negative consequences, which, according to the participants, should be taken into account when planning and implementing advocacy campaigns.

It should be especially noted that the design of the article implemented at this stage did not reveal significant differences in the perception of interpretations of a healthy lifestyle among the groups of respondents leading or not leading a healthy lifestyle. It is possible that this situation is associated with insufficiently objective indicators offered to respondents at the stage of selection for participation in focus groups - potential participants were asked to independently assess their lifestyle as healthy or not.⁷ Therefore, the use of self-assessment to determine the lifestyle of the respondent is not sufficiently objective. In the future, it is advisable to introduce specific objective indicators (the presence or absence of bad habits, the regularity and balance of nutrition, the frequency and nature of physical activity, adherence to the daily routine, the frequency of medical preventive examinations, etc.) when selecting respondents to participate in studies on similar topics.

Thus, the obvious relationship between health and lifestyle is especially relevant for young people. At the same time, using the example of a student audience, we can state the presence in the mass consciousness of at least two interpretations of a healthy lifestyle - minimalist and maximalist, which differ in

⁷ Student youth perception of health (the results of a survey)] // Moscow, 2014. p. 317—320.

the degree of compliance with certain components of a healthy lifestyle.

The understanding of the components of a healthy lifestyle among students corresponds to the generally accepted ones, but is perceived by the majority of respondents as a declared value. The relevance of a healthy lifestyle for the representatives of the youth audience is low due, mainly, to the absence of health problems.

From the above, it can be concluded that the functional capacity of students decreases after 21:30. Increased daily workload of students in their studies and personal life leads to chronic stress and weakens the body's protective functions, causing various diseases. In order to study and do your personal life properly, you need to get into a certain pattern and take a break when you work hard. Disorders of work, rest and diet can lead to pancreatitis, chronic cholecystitis, obesity, weight loss, rheumatism, diarrhea, ulcers, gallstones, flatulence, hepatitis and other diseases. In order to properly organize the style, you need to pay attention to the following:

- perform various activities on time;
- effective replacement of work and rest;
- Systematic rational nutrition;
- Abandonment of harmful habits;
- follow the rules of personal hygiene;
- 1-1.5 hours of sports every day;
- 2-3 hours of fresh air every day;
- follow the rules of hygiene when using information technology;
- Strict adherence to sleep hygiene.

In conclusion, the organization of a healthy lifestyle is important for all sectors of society today. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.

PQ-4887 of 10.11.2020 “On additional measures to ensure healthy nutrition of the population”, promotion of a healthy lifestyle in the country defined a number of tasks in order.⁸ The normative and legal acts adopted in the country on the reform of healthcare and physical culture and sports, along with the improvement of these systems, emphasize the formation of a healthy lifestyle among the population as one of the important directions of state policy in this area. In particular, the resolution provides for the development of the health care system, physical culture and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2025, prevention of non-communicable diseases by 2022, support for a healthy lifestyle and increasing physical activity. concepts and measures for the widespread implementation of a healthy lifestyle and the further development of mass sports were approved and implemented.

In order to strengthen the healthy lifestyle of students, it is advisable to do the following:

- organization of free sports clubs in each higher education institution, if any, to increase their diversity;
- determine the blood pressure, pulse, blood sugar of all students once a month in universities;
- organization of competitions in any sport once a month in universities;
- encouragement of students to lead a healthy lifestyle at the expense of the university fund (in the form of sportswear, school equipment or money);
- consider the proposals of students on a healthy lifestyle and reward the best bidders.

It is important to remember that the rules of a healthy lifestyle work in harmony, complement each other, and it is impossible to do without each other. If we follow it now, we will be able to take the first steps towards a healthy and happy life.

⁸ www.norma.uz

References:

1. Student youth perception of health (the results of a survey)] // Moscow, 2014. p. 317—320.
2. Mo‘minov R. Etnopedagogika i sovremennaya uzbekskaya shkola — M.: 2013.
3. Mamatqulov B. “Public health and health management” “Ilm Ziyoy” publishing house, 2019. Chapter 7 82- 100. Chapter 8 101- 116.
4. Buduk-ool LK Social and hygienic factors of students' lifestyle: scientific publication / Hygiene and Sanitation. - M., 2015. - Volume 94 N5UBZH015. - p.95-97.
5. Ermakova N. A., Melnichenko P. I. et al. Lifestyle and health of students: scientific publication // Hygiene and sanitation. - M., 2016. - p. 558-563.
6. M. Akhmatov, "Effective management of public sports in the system of continuing education" "Science and Technology" Tashkent 2015.
7. Aripova S.Kh., “Physiology and hygiene of youth” T. : “Science and technology” 2010.
8. Shenyazov R. A. A comprehensive integrated assessment of health status , image and quality of life of medical students // Dis. PhD - is the honey. Sciences. Tashkent, 2011. 112 p.
9. www.lex.uz
10. www.norma.uz
11. www.stat.uz